

POLICY AGAINST INFLATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. In this article, the selection of the anti-inflation policy regime in the conditions of Uzbekistan, the role of the Central Bank of Uzbekistan, the fact that inflation targeting is one of the most popular methods of conducting monetary policy, ensuring price stability, the inflation targeting regime allows achieving several macroeconomic goals, and refers to the base rate.

Key words. inflation, Central Bank of Uzbekistan, inflation targeting, monetary policy, price stability, key rate.

The choice of the anti-inflation policy regime in the conditions of Uzbekistan is explained by a number of reasons. Today, inflation targeting has shown itself as an effective mode of monetary credit policy and is the most consistent mode with the goal of ensuring price stability in the medium term.

Today, inflation targeting is one of the most popular methods of conducting monetary policy, and this method is used in more than 40 countries of the world. The word "Target" is derived from the English language and means "goal". The inflation target is set in the inflation targeting mode. In order to achieve the inflation target, monetary policy mechanisms are gradually transferred to this regime and used as an effective instrument to reduce inflation. In turn, the application of this regime can create additional conditions for strong and sustainable economic growth in the medium term by ensuring price stability. At the same time, the Central Bank determines the most appropriate inflation target and achieves it by applying monetary policy instruments, regular analysis of economic development and wide coverage of monetary policy plans.

This regime has its own accepted standards and procedures. For example, decision making with extensive use of macroeconomic analysis and forecasting system, use of floating exchange rate, communication policy principles, currency intervention strategy, etc. The Central Bank should establish the most appropriate target (for example, 5 percent inflation) and maintain this target using monetary and credit policy instruments. Ensuring price stability is one of the effective methods for transitioning to the inflation targeting regime, which, in turn, in accordance with the Law "On the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan", the banking system and payment systems of the Central Bank is among its main goals, such as ensuring the stability of its operation.

Why do most countries implement inflation targeting?

The fact is that low and predictable (stable) inflation is a very necessary factor for stable economic growth in the country. Consequently, the inflationary expectation is added to the interest rate when granting a loan by commercial banks, and a high inflationary expectation leads to a higher loan interest rate. Thus, high interest rates calculated for the use of borrowed funds (loans) by entrepreneurs (under the influence of high inflation) affect the payments related to their return. If the interest rates (calculated for the loan) are high, entrepreneurs will get less credit. This has a negative impact on long-term economic growth, affecting their ability to invest. After all, the investments we make today serve as an important tool in creating the main production resources used in the production of goods and services tomorrow. Low and predictable (stable) inflation is one of the necessary conditions for central banks for sustainable economic growth. Therefore, maintenance of low and predictable (stable) inflation is defined by most central banks as their long-term goal (target).

Why use inflation targeting?

The inflation targeting regime allows to achieve several macroeconomic goals:

- prevent sharp price increases and high inflation;
- formation of the money market, elimination of the causes of segmentation of the money market;
- supporting the solvency of the population and entrepreneurs and ensuring the stability of the financial sector, taking into account internal and external factors.

How is the inflation targeting regime implemented?

In order to implement the inflation targeting regime, first of all, the following conditions must be met:

- setting the permanent inflation target and communicating it to the general public (regularly inform the population about inflation, its factors and the expected inflation target)
- large-scale use of monetary policy instruments (REPO and currency swap auctions, deposit auctions, and Central Bank bond placement auctions) in order to control inflationary processes and regulate interest rates in the money market;
- detailed macroeconomic analysis for making objective decisions in the field of monetary policy (analysis of the state of economic entities: household sector, business sector, public administration sector and the outside world) and available in domestic and foreign markets forecasting based on open data;
- to improve the communication policy in order to convey the goals of monetary policy (price stability, popularity of loans, low level of inflation, increasing the confidence of the population in the national currency, etc.) .

What instruments of monetary policy are used in the conditions of the inflation targeting regime?

In order to maintain the level of inflation in the inflation targeting regime, money is one of the main instruments of credit policy, and it is the main rate determined by the Central Bank. By changing the key rate, the Central Bank can influence the interest rates offered by commercial banks on deposits and loans. This, in turn, affects the price level in the economy through aggregate demand.

Based on the above, inflation targeting means the process of announcing a predetermined inflation rate (target) to the general public, as well as the process of achieving and maintaining this indicator. The Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan is gradually moving to the inflation targeting regime, and in 2023 it is planned to reach the inflation target of 5 percent.

At the same time that the rate of inflation in Uzbekistan fell to a record level, in many countries of the world, on the contrary, it accelerated sharply. For example, in the United States it reached a record level 40 years ago, and in Russia five years ago. There are several reasons for this. The first, of course, is that almost all countries have eased monetary policy following the coronavirus pandemic. That is, the government began to pour more money into the economy - for example, in the form of direct payments to the population or cheap loans. As a result, demand for consumption is increasing, and production is lagging behind. Another reason is the devaluation of the national currency. For example, the Turkish lira has depreciated by almost 50 percent this year, causing inflation to exceed 20 percent. In this situation, the Uzbek soum is strong - in the first ten months, the currency depreciated by only two percent. Head of the Central Bank, Mamarizo Nurmatov, said that a relatively stable exchange rate was achieved as a result of a 35 percent increase in foreign exchange earnings due to exports, as well as an increase in the volume of currency exchange by banks and exporters. Such phenomena as a high share of state participation in the economy, a strong dependence on the export of raw materials, and structural imbalances can significantly accelerate the growth of prices of products and services, especially during the period of reforms. Inflation targeting is aimed at preventing this. The low level of inflation means price stability, which, in turn, has a positive effect on the standard of living of the population and its labor activity. It is expected that these factors will eventually increase the confidence of the population in the national currency, reduce the level of dollarization in the economy, and increase the volume of domestic and foreign investment.

In short, inflation occurs when the currency of a country depreciates. And of course, our government and the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan are consistently taking the

necessary measures to prevent and eliminate it. The inflation index in our country is decreasing year by year. Including, the inflation rate is 12.3% as of 2022. It is planned to reduce this indicator to 5% in the coming years, and in this regard, sufficient reforms are being carried out in our country. Therefore, we are confident that we will soon achieve this goal.

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